

Awareness and Usage of Right To Information (RTI) by Women Journalists

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Abstract

The origins of Right to Information Act can be traced to the 1990's. Over the course of time it underwent various changes and waves of evolution. Post 1990's, many state governments tried to formulate their own versions of the RTI. However, it was due to the efforts of social activist turned politician Arvind Kejriwal that the RTI Act came into existence in the year 2005. RTI has had also been subject of intense discussion and deliberations across academia, policy makers and bureaucrats for a large period. Despite restraints on certain information not accessible and obtainable for the people always, this Act is beneficial for a larger populace. The current research paper looks at awareness and usage of RTI by various women journalists who are working in various media organizations. The study employs quantitative research approaches in the form of survey.

Keywords: Awareness, Usage, Right to Information, Women journalists, Media

Introduction

RTI in India

Das P. K. (2006) gave meaning and interpretation of the words used in the Article 19 and clause (1) (a) of the Constitution of India of which Right to Information is the product. He concluded that government functions must be transparent and the three instrumentalities viz. executive, legislative and judiciary of the state should be prevented from deceiving people. Goel S. L. (2007)'s book delved into the Right to Information from different angles such as historical, legal, institutional, political, administrative and even futuristic. The book is not just a mere commentary on the Right to Information Act, 2005 with some introductory information in an extremely comprehensive manner.

Review of Literature

RTI

Acharya N. K. (2006) had commented on the procedure for seeking information and the fee structure to avail information through RTI.

He had also given the format of application, first appeal and second appeal for obtaining information and also given answers to queries. Mishra Sudhansu’s (2009) book spoke about the scope, different provisions, strengths and shortfalls of the RTI Act. The book also gives valuable information about how rural people could use RTI for their needs apart from their urban counterparts.

Methodology

The research study adopts quantitative research approaches in the form of survey.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the awareness of RTI among women journalists.
- To explore the usage of RTI by women journalists.

Analysis

Table 4.1 Respondents Details

Channel	Frequency	Percentage
Puthiya Thalaimurai TV	5	20
Polimer TV	5	20
Thanthi TV	5	20
News 7	5	20
News 18	5	20
Total	25	100

Figure 4.1

From Table 4.1 and figure 4.1, we can infer that there were equal number of respondents from Puthiya Thalaimurai TV, Polimer TV, Thanthi TV, News 7 and News 18 channels with 20% each.

Table 4.2 Awareness of RTI in news

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	25	100
No	0	0
Total	25	100

From Table 4.2 and figure 4.2, we can infer that all respondents were aware of RTI.

Figure 4.2

Table 4.3 Usage of RTI

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	9	36
No	16	64
Total	25	100

Figure 4.3

From Table 4.3 and figure 4.3, we can infer that only 36% of the respondents have used RTI. 64% of the respondents have not used RTI.

Table 4.4

Frequency of RTI related news in your organization's TV channel

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	0	0
Once in a while	0	0
Rarely	25	100

Figure 4.4

From Table 4.4 and figure 4.4, we can infer that all respondents rarely saw RTI related news in their organization’s TV channel.

Table 4.5 Information sought by RTI

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Journalists	0	0
Strangers/ other individuals	25	100
Total	25	100

Figure 4.5

From Table 4.5 and figure 4.5, we can infer that all the information sought by RTI were through strangers and other individuals.

Table 4.6 Information obtained by Journalists becoming news

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	4	16
No	21	84
Total	25	100

Figure 4.6

From Table 4.6 and figure 4.6, we can infer that only 16% of the information obtained through RTI by journalists became news. 84% of the information obtained did not become news.

Findings

- There were equal number of respondents from Puthiya Thalaimurai TV, Polimer TV, Thanthi TV, News 7 and News 18 channels with 20% each. (Table 4.1 and figure 4.1)
- All respondents were aware of RTI. (Table 4.2 and figure 4.2)
- 36% of the respondents have used RTI. 64% of the respondents have not used RTI. (Table 4.3 and figure 4.3)
- All respondents rarely saw RTI related news in their organization's TV channel. (Table 4.4 and figure 4.4)
- All the information sought by RTI were through strangers and other individuals. (Table 4.5 and figure 4.5)
- 16% of the information obtained through RTI by journalists became news. 84% of the information obtained did not become news. (Table 4.6 and figure 4.6)

Conclusion

The current research study was envisioned to investigate the awareness and usage of RTI among women journalists who are employed at various TV channels. The study revealed that despite awareness among women journalists about RTI only 36% of the respondents have used RTI to seek some information. All respondents agreed that RTI related news rarely appeared in their organization's TV channel. The study also revealed that all information sought by RTI were by strangers. Only 16% of the news obtained through RTI and by women journalists became news. This affirms that there is still widespread negligence from media outlets in telecasting news related to RTI.

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